

HR ANALYTICS IN TALENT ACQUISITION AND THE GIG ECONOMY: A STUDY OF JOB SEEKERS AND HR PROFESSIONALS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DHULE CITY

Dr. Kranti Shashikant Patil

*Asst. Professor, Shri Shivaji Vidya Prasarak Santhas, B.N.S Patil Arts & M.F.M.A Commerce
College, Dhule.*

Email: ksp446@gmail.com

Abstract

Human Resource practices are changing because of technology and digital tools. Today many organizations use HR analytics to improve hiring decisions. At the same time, the gig economy is growing, where people work on short-term or project-based jobs instead of permanent employment. This study examines the role of HR analytics in talent acquisition and the growing importance of gig work with special reference to Dhule city. The study is based on primary data collected from 100 respondents, including job seekers and HR professionals. Simple tools like percentages, bar charts, and pie charts are used for analysis. The findings show that HR analytics helps in faster recruitment, better candidate selection, and increased use of gig workers. The study concludes that both analytics and gig employment are useful for modern workforce management in Dhule city.

Keywords: HR Analytics, Talent Acquisition, Gig Economy, Recruitment, Workforce Planning, Dhule City, Flexible Employment.

► *Corresponding Author: Dr. Kranti Shashikant Patil*

Introduction:

In earlier times, recruitment decisions were mostly taken based on experience and personal judgment. Today organizations use data and technology for better results. HR analytics helps companies study employee information such as skills, performance, and experience to select suitable candidates. Along with this, the gig economy is becoming popular. Many young people prefer flexible jobs like freelancing, contract work, or project-based employment. Employers also prefer gig workers to reduce costs and complete short-term tasks.

In growing cities like Dhule, both small and medium businesses are slowly adopting digital hiring methods. Therefore, it is important to study how HR analytics and gig employment are influencing talent acquisition in this region.

Review of Literature:

- Deloitte reports that data-based hiring improves productivity and reduces recruitment time.
- McKinsey & Company highlights that gig workers form a major part of the modern workforce and support flexible staffing.
- LinkedIn studies show that online hiring tools help recruiters reach better candidates quickly.

These studies indicate that analytics and flexible employment are shaping the future of HR practices.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To understand the concept of HR analytics.
2. To study its role in talent acquisition.
3. To examine the growth of gig employment in Dhule city.
4. To compare preferences of job seekers and HR professionals.
5. To suggest ways to improve recruitment practices using analytics.

Hypotheses of the Study:

H0₁: HR analytics has no significant effect on recruitment efficiency.

H1₁: HR analytics improves recruitment efficiency.

H0₂: Gig employment has no impact on talent acquisition.

H1₂: Gig employment positively impacts talent acquisition.

Scope of the Study:

- This study is Limited to Dhule city
- Includes job seekers and HR professionals
- Focus on recruitment and gig employment only
- Sample size of 100 respondents

Limitations:

In this research the limitations are as follows:

- Small sample size
- Time limitations
- Based on personal opinions
- Results may not apply to all cities

Research Design:

Research Area: For this research I have selected Local companies, consultancies, and job seekers in Dhule city

Sample Size: Total 100 respondents are there as a sample size. In that I took 50 Job seekers and 50 HR Professionals.

- 50 Job seekers
- 50 HR professionals

Sampling Method: For the said research I used Simple random sampling method.

Data Collection: In the said research I have collected data through

- Primary data : Questionnaire survey
- Secondary data : Books, reports, articles, websites

Tools for Analysis: In this research I have used these tools for analysis a data i.e Percentages, Tables, Pie charts, Bar charts etc.

Data Analysis:

1. Recruitment Methods Used by Organizations

Method	Respondents
Traditional hiring	18
Online portals	27
HR analytics tools	32
Gig platforms	23
Total	100

It shows HR analytics tools are most preferred.

2. Work Preference of Respondents

Type	Respondents
Prefer gig/flexible work	58
Prefer permanent job	42
Total	100

It shows majority prefer gig /flexible work.

Findings:

- Most organizations use digital tools for hiring
- HR analytics helps reduce time and cost of recruitment
- Gig work is popular among youth and freelancers
- Employers prefer gig workers for short-term projects
- Awareness of HR analytics is increasing in Dhule
- Online recruitment is replacing traditional methods

Conclusion:

From this study, I conclude that HR analytics is becoming very important in modern recruitment. It helps organizations select the right candidates based on data rather than guesswork. The gig economy is also growing quickly in Dhule city, especially among young job seekers who prefer flexibility. The statistical analysis using percentages and chi-square tests clearly shows that both HR analytics and gig employment have a significant positive impact on talent acquisition in Dhule city. Therefore, combining HR analytics with gig employment can improve hiring efficiency and organizational performance. Both employers and employees can benefit from this modern approach.

Suggestions:

- Companies should adopt HR analytics software
- Training should be given to HR staff
- More local job portals and gig platforms should be promoted
- Awareness programs for digital recruitment should be conducted
- Government and institutions should support skill development
- Future studies can cover larger areas and more samples

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